

THE IMPORTANCE OF APPLYING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING READING FOR EFL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This article reflects the use of authentic reading materials in teaching EFL learners. It is emphasized that teaching a natural, modern foreign language is only possible with materials derived from the lives of native speakers or created in accordance with established and used speech standards while taking into account the cultural and mentalities of native speakers.

Reading is a sort of receptive speech activity that involves the perception, processing, and comprehension of a written (authentic) text. To master the linguistic material, students employ reading as a learning method. The introduced language content is consolidated, pronunciation skills are stabilized and enhanced, speech flow is meaningfully split and intoned, vocabulary and grammar abilities are strengthened, and linguistic and semantic conjecture is established during the reading process.

The traditional interpretation is the most commonly used approach to understanding authenticity in methodology of teaching a foreign language, when materials created by native speakers of the target language are considered authentic, but later found their application in the process of teaching a foreign language without any processing or transformation. Outside of the language

context, a language that emphasizes a communication approach [1;p.148]. The primary goal of authentic texts is to elicit responses from students. It's worth noting that a single text can be employed at many levels of education, taking into consideration all pupils' skills. The goal of employing real texts is to raise students' knowledge levels, which can be accomplished by switching from adapted to authentic instructional materials.

Students who are studying a foreign language inevitably experience a sense of curiosity, followed by an interest in not just new ways of communicating the subject they already know, but also in native speakers of the language being studied, their lifestyles, ways of living, and so on. As a result, employing authentic texts is the most effective way to encourage kids [2;p.127].

Authentic texts have the advantage of immersing pupils in a real-life setting by creating an environment of travel or commercial connections. "The language is more modern in foreign versions, closer to spoken English, full of new terms and idioms, and this is natural because they were produced by native speakers" [3:p.63]. Students will encounter a limitless amount of unfamiliar or wholly new words, idioms, and structures in authentic educational materials. Students must semantize lexical units autonomously using context or word formation analysis.

The fundamental purpose of authentic materials is to allow pupils to experience using the known to understand the unfamiliar on a regular basis. The teacher can efficiently create foreign language cultural competence while motivating pupils to study by employing actual texts in English courses. The teacher should use the general didactic and methodological principles of teaching a foreign language when selecting resources for a lesson.

The value of authentic texts as a means of teaching is evident; they have been extensively studied in the scientific literature, both by domestic (R.R. Papakhina, D.A. Eshboeva) [4:p.278] and international methodologists: (K. Morrow, D. Harmer).

1. Authentic writings lessen the chance of foreign language reality being distorted.
2. The language used in authentic literature functions as a tool of genuine communication.
3. Information provided with the help of authentic texts in a non-linguistic setting has a high level of authority due to the lack of a didactic focus.

Separately, we underline that teaching a natural, modern foreign language is only

possible with materials derived from the lives of native speakers or created in accordance with established and used speech standards while taking into account the cultural and mentalities of native speakers. [5:p.13].

The following conditions must be met by materials used to teach foreign languages:

1. Information that is useful and entertaining to pupils and can help them become more motivated.
2. Material content that is appropriate for students' age and psychological traits, as well as their speech experience in both their native and foreign languages
3. Representation of many types of speech
4. The realistic portrayal of individuals, places, and circumstances in actual content.
5. The occurrence of redundant information pieces.
6. An authentic text's ability to elicit a response.
7. The presence of educational value is desirable .

Preference should be given to authentic texts that reflect the conversational style of everyday speech when selecting materials for educating high school students. Lexical units and their literary equivalents should be introduced before reading the text (during the pre-text stage). Students must also get familiar with examples of typical genres / types of texts, demonstrating the linguistic and logical-compositional elements of their application in the foreign language under study. The learner must get the required information about the nation of the language being studied and its inhabitants in order to acquire background knowledge and create sociolinguistic and sociocultural abilities on this basis. Various periodicals,

newspapers, and articles about the people's lives, traditions, and values in the country where the language is learned might be used as a source.

While many methodologists feel that methodical processing of educational materials is acceptable and even desirable, they also believe that these materials must fit very particular conditions. These requirements include the use of authentic lexical units, phraseology, and grammar, the text's required logical coherence, the correspondence of the language means used to the proposed situation, the reality of this situation, the reflection of the peculiarities of native speakers' national mentality and culture, informative and emotional richness, and so on. These and other text authenticity criteria separate a complete composition from a collection of sentences.

When picking real books for school classes, the instructor considers the following factors:

- what can cause difficulties for students (linguistic, content, evaluative), and if there are a large number of difficulties, the understanding of the aesthetic value of the selected literary text decreases, so techniques to remove these difficulties in perceiving the text should be used;
- whether the teacher personally likes this text or not, and why;
- whether students need prior knowledge to understand the text;
- whether the text's content touches on topics that may be related to students' life experiences (similarities, differences);
- what can pique students' interest, excite them emotionally, etc.;
- whether the text reflects the realities of the country of the language being studied, its culture, way of life, customs, etc.;

- whether the text reinforces existing traditional knowledge about the country

Reading, then, plays an important part in the teaching of foreign languages since the student comprehends and analyzes the information read from the text while conducting this sort of speech action. The development and improvement of reading techniques, which are characterized by good speed, corresponding to the type of reading, accompanied by a complete understanding of the student, and carried out with a minimum expenditure of reading strength, is the end result of teaching reading, which all foreign language teachers undoubtedly strive for.

Working with authentic text is a time-consuming process. Creating conditions for understanding the substance of the text as a whole, building guessing and guessing skills, and developing the ability to ignore language obstacles are the major tasks in working with it. The development of intercultural and interpersonal communication skills might start with an authentic text.

There are three steps of working with real material: pre-text, text, and post-text [6:p.59]. The pre-text stage's goal is to pique students' interest in learning more about the text. We propose utilizing in order to avoid any linguistic issues. The text's linguistic means are carefully chosen for these types of exercises (the realities of the country of the language being studied, carrying historical and cultural information, lexical units). The context is broadened by the insertion of new material, and the text's information appears to unfold: photos, footnotes, and links can all be employed. Pre-text work comprises an overview of the scenario,

setting the tone for reading, reading and studying the author's biography, as well as the text itself.

A pre-text exercise system. The teacher awakens pupils' background knowledge on a particular issue by asking numerous questions on the text's theme. This causes the reader to anticipate the text's content. Visual elements can be used to captivate the attention of kids. Pre-text preparation might also include alterations to the text's title or organization. In general, the preliminary stage entails activities such as familiarization with the glossary and the name of the text's broad topic; guessing the text's content from the title; using the keyword scheme to predict the text's content and title it; determining the text's theme from illustrations. respond to inquiries that neatly leads to the text's subject; identify the word in the title that expresses the author's opinion.

The reading of the text comes after the pre-text stage (text). At this point, we believe it is necessary to accurately formulate the tasks for the proposed text. The following are some examples of tasks: Guess the topic of the entire text from the first paragraph; find a sentence in the first paragraph of the text that contains the main information; read the text and select lexical units on the topic; identify the sentences in which the text's topic is most revealed; create a text plan, giving titles to each of the text's paragraphs, and so on.

The final stage of text editing (post-text). The important job at this point is for the pupil to share their thoughts on what they have read. The purpose is to improve students' knowledge and skills in semantic text processing. We advocate employing text and imitative-reproductive exercises at this stage. We advocate employing productive creative exercises, role-playing games, project work, and other activities to consolidate the learned material and improve the motivation of students' creative activity.

Students can: express the text's primary idea; declare whether they agree with the author's opinion; explain the title of the text based on what they read; describe what is happening in the text (retell it) during such tasks. Discuss the emotional states of the characters; write a hero's dialogue or a monologue statement for one of the heroes; extract and analyze interesting material from the story, and so on.

To summarize, reading authentic texts and completing appropriate sets of exercises has a positive effect on the emotional state of the student's personality, and reading also solves pragmatic tasks such as activating and enriching vocabulary, expanding sociocultural competence, and improving the process of mastering a foreign language with the help of additional motivation.

References:

1. Zhoglina G.G. Development of communicative competence skills based on the use of authentic video documents: French language, language university: dis. ... cand. ped. Sciences. Pyatigorsk, 1998.p.147-156
2. Kazantseva G.N. Methods of studying attitudes to academic subjects // Foreign language at school. 2007. No. 7.p/127-135

3. Meshcheryakova E.V. The role of the modern socio-cultural situation in the process of preparing the future educator (on the material of the English language): a theoretical and methodological study. Volgograd: Change, 1999.p.63
4. Papakhina R.R. The use of authentic materials in teaching English // Education and training: theory, methodology and practice: Sat. Materials VIII Intern. scientific-practical. conf. (Cheboksary, November 6, 2016). Cheboksary: Interactive Plus, 2016, pp. 278–279.
6. Meshcheryakova E.V., Isaeva I.S. Linguistic and didactic potential of a blog in teaching English // Modern problems of science and education. 2015. No. 4. P. 59.
7. Harmer J. How to teach English. London: Pearson. 2010.